

BIM

prove

D3.3 – Proof of concept system description and test results

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 958450. This document reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Project Title	Improving Building Information Modelling by Realtime Tracing of Construction Processes
Project Acronym	BIMprove
Grant Agreement No	958450
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	Industrial Sustainability
Start Date of Project	1st September 2020
Duration of Project	36 Months

Name and Number of the deliverable	3.3 - Proof of concept system description and test results
Related WP number and name	WP 3 - Integration, testing & piloting
Deliverable dissemination level	Public
Deliverable due date	28 February 2022
Deliverable submission date	28 February 2022
Task leader/Main author	Ruprecht Altenburger (ZHAW)
Contributing partners	All
Reviewer(s)	Jens Birkevold (SINTEF)

Abstract

This deliverable describes technical developments up to M18 - the middle of the project - and shows the proof of concept for different parts of the BIMprove system. The main functionality of BIMprove is an extensive semi-automated data acquisition of various sizes and its processing. Mainly geometry data, but also photos, thermal image data, data of people and devices are captured or recorded. Therefore, this deliverable deals mainly with the topics "data collection" and "data processing".

Keywords

Proof of concept, data processing, BIM, testing, construction processes

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	29.01.2022	Initial version	Ruprecht Altenburger (ZHAW), Michael Peter (ZHAW)
v0.2	16.2.2022	Correction	Miquel Cantero (ROBI), Kaj Helin (VTT), Michael Peter (ZHAW), Dag Fjeld Edvardsen (CATENDA), Matthias Aust (FhG-IAO), Anu Purhonen (VTT)
V1.0	28.2.2022	Approved, final version	Jens Birkevold (SINTEF)

Disclaimer

This document is provided with no warranties whatsoever, including any warranty of merchantability, non-infringement, fitness for any particular purpose, or any other warranty with respect to any information, result, proposal, specification or sample contained or referred to herein. Any liability, including liability for infringement of any proprietary rights, regarding the use of this document or any information contained herein is disclaimed. No license, express or implied, by estoppel or otherwise, to any intellectual property rights is granted by or in connection with this document. This document is subject to change without notice. BIMprove has been financed with support from the European Commission. This document reflects only the view of the author(s) and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
PUC	Pilot Use Case
PTZ	Pan-Tilt-Zoom
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
PoC	Proof of Concept
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
SVG	Scalable Vector Graphics
ROS	Robot Operating System
PCL	Point Cloud
API	Application Programming Interface
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
BIM	Building Information Modelling
IR	InfraRed
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
DOF	Degree of Freedom
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
CNN	Convolutional neural network
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
GUI	Graphical User Interface
BCF	BIM Collaboration Format

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

Contents

1. Introduction.....	10
2. Data Acquisition.....	11
2.1. Spatial Data Capture with Ground Robots	11
2.1.1. Related Challenges and UGV Preparation.....	12
2.1.2. Summary	20
2.2. Evacuation Route Check	20
2.2.1. Summary	21
2.3. Spatial Data Capture with Drones	21
2.3.1. Indoor geometry data capture	23
2.3.2. Results	23
2.3.3. Summary	24
2.4. Data capture for detecting safety nets, VIAS-site, Spain.....	24
2.4.1. Planning the Mission	24
2.4.2. Cleaning & Cropping the interested areas of point cloud (point cloud) ...	26
2.4.3. Aligning measured data to the BIM-model (photos and point clouds).....	26
2.4.4. Summary	27
2.5. IR - Image data capture.....	28
2.5.1. FLIR Vue Pro thermal camera.....	28
2.5.2. FLIR Ax8 thermal camera (Ground Robot)	29
2.5.3. Summary	30
2.6. Indoor Positioning System.....	31
2.6.1. Dataflow and overview of data processing steps in the PoC setup.....	32
2.6.2. Results	33
2.6.3. Summary	35
3. Data Processing and Evaluation	36
3.1. Detecting Safety Nets.....	36
3.1.1. Evaluation Metrics	36
3.1.2. Evaluation Results.....	38

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

3.1.3.	Evaluation Conclusions	39
3.1.4.	Summary	40
3.2.	Scan versus plan	40
3.2.1.	Summary	43
3.3.	BIMprove and the web application	43
3.3.1.	Summary	44
3.4.	Scheduling and BIM	45
3.4.1.	Summary	46
3.5.	Daily Decisions	46
3.5.1.	Summary	48
3.6.	Virtual Reality	49
3.6.1.	Testing methods and results	49
3.6.2.	Usability expert tests	49
3.6.3.	User tests	49
3.6.4.	Performance tests and -optimisation	52
3.6.5.	BIM models: Optimisation strategies depending on the use case	52
3.6.6.	Point Clouds	52
3.6.7.	Open points and next steps	53
3.6.8.	Summary	54
4.	Summary and evaluation of the proof of concept	55

Index of Figures

Figure 1	FLIR AX8 IR camera	12
Figure 2	Site visit on HRS construction site Zurich. The floor is of good quality, but there are high thresholds that pose a difficulty for the robot.	13
Figure 3	SUMMIT XL-HL on VIAS construction site in Madrid (PoC testing)	13
Figure 4	Tags for localisation on VIAS construction site in Madrid (PoC testing)	15
Figure 5	Snapshot of picture metadata	16
Figure 6	Robotnik HMI for robot operation	17
Figure 7	Registration report of the Leica Cyclone software	18

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 8 Transport of robot to the 2nd floor with a platform on crane	19
Figure 9 Registration of point clouds	20
Figure 10 Visualisation of possible route	21
Figure 11 a) Pipe installations in ZHAW lab, b) VIAS site/Madrid overview, c) Safety nets at VIAS site, d) Foam board installations at ZHAW lab.....	22
Figure 12 Comparison of model and measured/generated 3D data. The photogrammetry software has problems to extract 3D information based on the images. Especially on the homogeneous pipes there is hardly any 3D point to see	23
Figure 13 Planning a mission in Pix4D3DCapture: View on VIAS site in Madrid. Buildings on the neighbouring properties help with orientation and planning.....	25
Figure 14 a) Indoors: Point of View photos used for t_Stairs.las, b) Outdoors: Point of View photos used for t_SideView.las	27
Figure 15 a) Indoors: t_Stairs.las vs. Architecture_zeroed_from_rev_0.ifc, b) Outdoors: t_SideView.las vs. Architecture_zeroed_from_rev_0.ifc.....	27
Figure 16 The new generation of the 2DOF gimbal equipped with the FLIR Vue IR camera.	28
Figure 17 Thermal and corresponding standard images from the ZHAW lab.....	29
Figure 18 Optical and IR-image in Robotnik lab	30
Figure 19 BLE Indoor Positioning device.....	32
Figure 20 Data processing in PoC	32
Figure 21 Indoor positioning PoC layout.....	33
Figure 22 Visualisation of localisation data.....	33
Figure 23 Developing Mean Average Precision, mAP@0.5 and mAP@0.95 with 960x960 and 640x640 image input sizes. The achieved maximum mAP@0.5 is around 0.75 and a little less than 0.5 for the 960x960 and 640x640 image sizes, respectively. The mAP@0.5-0.95 reaches levels of over 0.5 and 0.25, respectively.	38
Figure 24 Final precision-recall graphs for detected object classes with a) 960x960 and b) 640x640 image input sizes. The model reaches 0.946 and 0.696 mean average precision, mAP for safety-net detection depending on the image size used. Results are after 200 training epochs using the best model achieved during the training.	38
Figure 25 Validation losses reached on the validation data subset for the image sizes of 960x960 and 640x640 pixels.....	39
Figure 26 Matching points (shown here in total) after BIM-based oriented bounding box mapping	41
Figure 27 Residual points after BIM-based oriented bounding box mapping. Viewed from a different angle than Fig. 26	41
Figure 28 Comparing scan vs plan manually in the model server GUI. The column "inside" the point cloud is selected with its green highlight colour showing through.....	42

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 29 Same as in panel a, but with the point cloud points being semi-transparent.....	42
Figure 30 The start page of the BIMprove web application	44
Figure 31 The schedule page allows linking tasks and objects in the BIM	45
Figure 32 User interface in the BCF server (Bimsync) of the issues created in one of the BIMprove test projects.....	46
Figure 33 Screenshot of a task for the decision maker to consider (currently in the model server GUI)	47

Index of Tables

Table 1 The decision makers has to make a choice on how to proceed	47
Table 2 Planned test for PoC.....	50
Table 3 Point cloud dilemma.....	53
Table 4 Summary of PoC results	55

1. Introduction

In general, data acquisition is not the goal itself, but is very closely linked to the needs and processes of the construction process. For this reason, the following PoC (Proof of Concept) cases always have a close link between the measurement process and its evaluation. The tests described use data recorded in laboratories as well as at the pilot construction site in Madrid. This site was originally planned for safety aspects only. However, the data shown also describes thematic areas such as construction scheduling and construction progress. The pilot construction sites play a very central role in the entire BIMprove project. The test cases shown here are associated with them. The pilot use cases (PUC) that will take place in the second half of the project are listed here again:

- PUC Safety, at VIAS construction site in Madrid/Spain
- PUC Fire prevention, at HRS construction site in Lausanne/Switzerland
- PUC Scheduling at AFG construction site in Oslo/Norway

In the following 12 test cases are described and presented after each other. First focusing on Data Acquisition, followed by Data Processing and Evaluation.

2. Data Acquisition

2.1. Spatial Data Capture with Ground Robots

Specific features related to the ground robot system were already described in D2.2

As a short summary, the ground robot selected, SUMMIT XL-HL is a robotic platform for application development with great versatility and resistance. The robot has skid-steering kinematics based on 4 high power motor wheels.

The platform can navigate autonomously or teleoperated and can be configured with a wide range of sensors as it also has internal (USB, RS232, GPIO) and external connectivity (USB, RJ45, power supplies 5,12 VDC and battery) to add custom components easily.

In the context of BIMprove, a mechanical adaptation has been made in order to place an additional high precision laser scanner. The stability of different devices in a higher position is at focus here. A short mention on the embedded sensors used for the data capture (besides the ones used for navigation) follows:

- PTZ camera: AXIS M5525 has a HDTV 1080p resolution, 10x optical zoom, and continuous 360° pan that lets you easily follow moving objects. AXIS M5525-E provides both the zoomed-in detail and the broad overview needed.
- Leica BLK 360 Imaging LaserScanner: In addition to the laser scanner used for navigation and obstacle avoidance, a Leica BLK360 imaging laser scanner has been selected as the main sensorics payload for the UGV. The main features of the laser are:
 1. High, standard and fast resolutions
 2. Weighs 1 kg / Size 165 mm tall x 100 mm diameter
 3. Less than 3 minutes for full-dome scan (in standard resolution) and 150 MP spherical image generation
 4. 360,000 laser scan setpoints per second
 5. High-Dynamic Range (HDR) and thermal imaging

A new addition to this list coming from the specific added value on the PoC is a Thermal Imaging Camera for Continuous Condition and Safety Monitoring.

- FLIR AX8 combines thermal imaging with a visual camera in one small, affordable package for continuous temperature monitoring and alarming.

Figure 1 FLIR AX8 IR camera

2.1.1. Related Challenges and UGV Preparation

While preparing and tuning several different processes of the robotic system needed for the autonomous inspection and data gathering, the main challenges confronted are:

2.1.1.1 *Autonomous navigation / path planning*

Within the current features of selected robot SUMMIT-XL, the autonomous navigation and path-planning challenges are already addressed in a number of ways.

As described in D2.2, the robot software architecture at this level uses the ROS navigation stack. The *robot_localization* package defines the source inputs and Kalman filter parameters for the robot location estimation, which can use different sensor sources for the location estimation. Then, the *robot_navigation* package defines the set of sensors used for obstacle avoidance and also the global and local planners required to implement navigation missions.

A first piece of knowledge, coming from the first contact to pilot sites performed in HRS site (see Fig. 2) in Switzerland, is that 3D environment acknowledgement was needed for the robot to navigate safely in some areas.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 2 Site visit on HRS construction site Zurich. The floor is of good quality, but there are high thresholds that pose a difficulty for the robot.

This is especially true wherever the robot can encounter obstacles at different heights and out of the 2D plane of a 2D laser scanner. Thus, the first change introduced on the hardware was the substitution of 2D Hokuyo UTM 30 in favour of Robosense RS-16 3D laser scanner.

Figure 3 SUMMIT XL-HL on VIAS construction site in Madrid (PoC testing)

It is worth mentioning that within the preparation work, a new approach opposed to regular tools such as the Cartographer tool was tested and tuned from scratch for this specific robotic system.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Cartographer is a system that provides real-time simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) in 2D and 3D across multiple platforms and sensor configurations.

Within the PoC we could evaluate the performance of the different approaches.

2.1.1.2 *Coordinate frames*

A clear challenge in common for all the data capturing means is fitting the results within the same coordinate system. This is not only true for showing results, but also for preparing the mission.

When it comes to our mobile robot system, the problem acquires multiple dimensions.

- The mobile robot has its own navigation map. The origin of this map is always created with the first localization when the internal mapping tool is triggered. Normally a teleoperated process of mapping the area is needed before the first robot mission within some location (this is not always needed depending on tools such as the Cartographer, where navigation and mapping could be simultaneously performed).
- Any given goal for the robot should refer to the navigation map. If it is not, robot could travel to unknown locations. Because of that a transformation should be put in place.
- The same transformation is then needed for the sensor data. It could be the case that some sensors are already calculated in the robot kinematic chain, which can solve the problem partially as the transformation is covering the whole chain. Some standalone sensors still have to transform the data.

As for the PoC works, different approaches have been followed in order to reach a solution. The fact that a pre-existing coordinate system is available within the IFC models is conditioning the work.

Part of this work was already described in D2.2. As a short recap, we created an integration that gets an updated 2D map-view of the physical space generated in the BIMsync platform.

This integration allows obtaining an SVG file and modifying its elements to adapt it to the format required by *map_server*, in order to be interpretable by the robot.

The SVG can be programmatically cleaned up from information not needed (text labels, different floors, doors...) and then exported to a .png-file image used as an input for the *map_server* node.

Further work on this approach has consisted of matching the config file with parameters so that scale is coincidental. Identifying visual marks on site in order to initialize the robot's pose was the next step, thanks to our so-called "marker mapping" tool.

Figure 4 Tags for localisation on VIAS construction site in Madrid (PoC testing)

Still remains an open point a last transformation between the lower left corner pixel of the navigation map, to the IFC origin in order to precisely locate the robot and thus the full kinematic chain.

2.1.1.3 Data Registration

Special focus has been put to the methods developed in order to perform the data registration.

2.1.1.4 Images

An automated way of retrieving images is a desirable feature for every robotic system.

While this is already solved for a number of devices within the current payload portfolio of the SUMMIT-XL, some work was needed in order to integrate new sensors.

The *image_pipeline* is an open-source project available for the ROS community. Once the camera drivers are available in ROS, the *image_view* package allows you to record images and videos coming from the raw data already available in a topic. Ethernet cameras are making things easier in this regard, as the camera drivers are straightforward to be used.

Then, a link must be established between the images captured and the robot localization. A previous step before the backend integration (on how to read the metadata), is being able to record it. In this regard, two different python codes in the form of new ROS packages have been put in place. First one works in order to retrieve the robot odometry and localization whenever the camera's recording

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

is triggered and then listing the image file names with this information. In this way we are recording the data as follows:

picture_file_name, timestamp, task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w

The second package will record the full trajectory of the robot in a file, in the form of a “poses” list together with an epoch timestamp for each one.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	20220217085245.jpeg, 1644944583026597159, bea86486-8f08-11ec-b909-0242ac120002, 41.6360296746,							
2	72.8506905495, 0.369945996444, -0.00193931666565, 0.130569923933, 0.0140495016215,							
3	0.991337654646, 0, 0							
4	...							
5	20220217085304.jpeg, 1644944601556248811, bea86486-8f08-11ec-b909-0242ac120002, 43.1184052376,							
6	72.7659450358, 0.370012820242, -0.00751672426387, 0.130305156697, 0.0570628602883,							
7	0.989801947346, 0, 0							
8	...							
9	20220217085310.jpeg, 1644944608089772092, bea86486-8f08-11ec-b909-0242ac120002, 43.8828532078,							
10	72.8275501546, 0.370019871962, -0.00700283151898, 0.130337915552, 0.0531862416116,							
11	0.990017278548, 0, 0							

Figure 5 Snapshot of picture metadata

2.1.1.5 LaserScan data

As introduced in D2.2, a Leica BLK360 imaging laser scanner has been selected as the main sensorics payload for the UGV. Mounting of a such dedicated solution ensures high performance and easier PCL handling as opposed to an in-house solution using the same navigation lidars (Laser Scanner).

Equally important as for the image capturing is having an automated way of triggering the LaserScan data capturing. In this way, the Leica solution has proved to be a valuable selection when it comes to its developer API. Not being fully public, an effort has been made towards this specific collaboration. The acknowledgement and gratitude is also going to the Leica developers facilitating the existing libraries.

On our side it is important to remark that a dedicated library has been created within the BIMprove Project in order to call the Leica library methods from the robot’s ROS system.

ROS services can now be called in order to trigger scans with different parameters but also recording the data on-the-go without processing the files in the proprietary software.

This is still an ongoing work, and several flaws of such integration are to be solved.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 6 Robotnik HMI for robot operation

It is important to note that these automatic processes provide either .blk recording (with or without images) or a raw .csv point cloud (PCL), which has to be transformed with additional tools such as CloudCompare. In any case the data recording will be independent and related to the position where they were captured. No stitching or processing is made here.

The previous point also leads to an interesting discussion on the data processing.

While having the data recorded automatically, or even retrieving a PCL in basic .csv files is really interesting, there is a good reason for proprietary software being used - since there is a clear and usually user-friendly workflow. Clearing or tuning the files (e.g. when data capture was not optimal) but also stitching large point clouds is not trivial. Other tools and processes such as aligning coordinate frames or transforming data formats are also very important for the potential use of the data. The value of having a human in-the-loop is also a topic of discussion as the quality of the results are really affected by the use of such software from a human operator (i.e. manual stitching can provide higher accuracy of the dataset).

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

2.1.1.6 PoC Results

Figure 7 Registration report of the Leica Cyclone software

In the following sections we will provide some highlights coming from the robot operation in the test site from VIAS in Madrid, as well as from some specific tests involving the full robotic system with PoC testing.

2.1.1.6.1 Environment

Other than the challenges previously identified we could remark some issues arise from the on-site tests:

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

- Service Stairs and accesses: it is common that construction sites have no other access to different floors but a service stair part of the scaffolding, which is normally steep and narrow. This can be an important impediment to the robot operation within different areas of the site. Until now we assume that the robot will be placed within the to-be-inspected floor. A crane with a tray might be used for that purpose (see following picture).

Figure 8 Transport of robot to the 2nd floor with a platform on crane

- The same thing applies for closed doors, whenever the robot has to cross them. Up to this moment we assume that the areas to inspect will be within robot's reach.
- Regarding obstacles, a 3D obstacle avoidance was implemented. Robot should be able to create a traversability map and identify not only obstacles but also holes or slopes. If an obstacle is preventing the robot to reach the place, an alarm will be communicated, and the robot will try to find an alternative path. If that can be found within a timeout, the mission will be cancelled.
- Storing the robot at the site could be a possibility. Given the delicate (and expensive) hardware on-board, a dedicated box for the system could be an added value. Recharging the robot while in the box is a feature to explore as well.

2.1.1.6.2 3D Geometry Data

A full dataset coming from the Leica BLK360 imaging laser scanner was taken at VIAS premises. The data was recorded on a 5 waypoint mission commanded through the robot HMI. The mission plan was created with the Sequencing tool, where the robot was commanded to reach the point and then wait for the scan to finish before proceeding to the next waypoint. In this case the data was

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

stored in the BLK device and forwarded to the FIELD 360 proprietary tool in order to stitch all the setups.

The scans were done including non-HDR pictures, taking 2 minutes and 50 seconds each. A maximum of 40 seconds was used in order to travel between the waypoints and trigger the next scan. The total operation took less than 17 minutes and the resulting bundle consists of 57 347 368 points. The point cloud after automated and manual link creation has a bundle accuracy of 2mm nevertheless, the points overlapped less than expected.

Figure 9 Registration of point clouds

2.1.2. Summary

PoC description		Main Result	Open Points
Spatial Capture Ground Robots	Data with	5 waypoints missions and point cloud bundle retrieved. Position data linked to images.	Alignment of coordinate frames. Scan data optionally fetched automatically was not always working, API to be checked. Missions imported through backend.

2.2. Evacuation Route Check

A different part of the PoC involved the ground robot ability to follow a path or even create the optimal one for a given waypoint.

We wanted to explore how this can help on maintaining a specified route obstacle-free (raising an alarm if it is not) and then suggesting alternative routes to the exit from random positions where the robot could be placed.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

As a first step, a dedicated software method was developed in order to create an alarm (in a robot topic) and take a picture of the obstacle that obliged the robot to change its route. The feature was successfully tested in VIAS premises.

On the other hand, further work was carried out in order to create an optimal plan from a random position and then follow it checking for obstacles. This last test was also repeatedly performed thanks to a simulation of the VIAS premises (created from an IFC file).

Figure 10 Visualisation of possible route

2.2.1. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Evacuation route check	Alarms and pictures taken successfully Optimal paths calculated and followed in simulation.	Routes to be shared in visualization tool (VR). Alternate exits included in the optimal paths.

2.3. Spatial Data Capture with Drones

The basic capabilities of the developed indoor UAVs have been shown in previous deliverables and demos (e.g. D2.1, "Development of stationery, ground and UAV based data acquisition systems"). The drones run with a flexible software where new requirements, sensors and tasks can be implemented. Here a further step, the integration of the UAV data capture system to the overall

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

BIMprove system is tested and evaluated. Further steps are being taken to incorporate this data collection system into the overall construction process. Also, further data processing of the captured data is tested and evaluated. These capabilities are shown with the following PoC use cases.

- Spatial data capture for pipe installations, done in a lab environment at ZHAW.
- Spatial data capture for geometry validation at VIAS construction site Madrid/Spain. This is performed with a commercial drone system (DJI Mavic II Pro) at VIAS site Madrid/Spain.
- Photo acquisition for AI-based detection of safety nets. This is performed with a commercial drone system (DJI Mavic II Pro) at VIAS site Madrid/Spain.
- Capturing different stages of foam-boards installation in lab environment at ZHAW. This is further processed for scheduling issues in the BIMprove system.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 11 a) Pipe installations in ZHAW lab, b) VIAS site/Madrid overview, c) Safety nets at VIAS site, d) Foam board installations at ZHAW lab

2.3.1. Indoor geometry data capture

Here we face several challenges at the same time. Such as:

- Mission and path planning based on previous captured data and an actual BIM model (development ongoing)
- Stable and robust flight with a local path planner for obstacle avoidance (development ongoing)
- Capturing geometrical data of high quality (surface/structure and lightning)
- Aligning the data in an optimal fashion to the BIM coordinate frame

2.3.2. Results

As in other measurements before, difficulties are shown in photogrammetry in low light conditions and homogeneous surfaces. In this test case, this was also observed and was even more apparent.

The photos were taken under different lightning conditions on a cloudy day (no sufficient lightning from outdoors):

1. Only ceiling lamp enabled.
2. Additional lamps positioned below the pipes pointing towards the ceiling.

Due to the additional contrast the resulting point clouds from experiment 2. were slightly denser than from experiment 1. The comparison below shows the *.ifc model vs. the point cloud from experiment 2. next to one of the pictures used to generate the point cloud via photogrammetry. It can be seen that the photogrammetry software has difficulties in finding appropriate contrasts, since the tubes also do not have any surface structure.

This test case clearly shows the limitations of 3D point cloud generation using photogrammetry indoors.

Figure 12 Comparison of model and measured/generated 3D data. The photogrammetry software has problems to extract 3D information based on the images. Especially on the homogeneous pipes there is hardly any 3D point to see

2.3.3. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Drone flight at specific small area to check pipe installations	Semi-autonomous drone flight, path planning from application.	Coordinate frames alignment, quality of p.c. (density and precision). When the captured data and the BIM are properly aligned, the results are satisfactory. A yet unsolved problem is the quality of point clouds, if lighting conditions are bad or there are mainly homogeneous surfaces (which will be the case on construction sites).

2.4. Data capture for detecting safety nets, VIAS-site, Spain

2.4.1. Planning the Mission

There are different tools to plan outdoor drone flights. We used apps provided by Pix4D namely *Pix4DCapture*. An app for smartphone or tablet, that allows image capture with drones for missions outside. The following pictures show screenshots of the mission planning process. One can choose several mission types (e.g. single grid, double grid, polygon mission). With a graphical input you define where the mission should take place. One difficulty here is that construction sites on site look quite different from those on the underlying satellite data, which are usually several years old. It is then sometimes difficult to locate correctly and has to be oriented to other waypoints. Giving additional information like drone- and camera type, flight altitude and image overlap, the app calculates desired flying paths, camera orientation and camera triggers. This data is automatically transferred to the drone.

Figure 13 Planning a mission in Pix4D3DCapture: View on VIAS site in Madrid. Buildings on the neighbouring properties help with orientation and planning

After processing photos of a scene to a point cloud using photogrammetry (Pix4D) the generated output is the point cloud as well as position and orientation information from the used photos with regards to a specific measurement frame (M) stored as a *.txt file:

- **Indoors (GPS denied environment):** It is recommended to place markers clearly visible within the captured scene (e.g. chilli tags for Pix4D). The user can then define a custom measurement frame (M). Including markers also increases precision of the measured point cloud. Furthermore, the scale of the measured point clouds is also adjusted by using markers. It is also recommended to do the image acquisition when the light condition is perfect, meaning that the light is even and balanced through all the surfaces of the structure, and try to avoid direct sunshine to the structure itself. If this is not capable, it is also recommended to accomplish the image acquisition as fast as possible. This is due to the change of light angle (shadow), which is normally the case in the construction site, that will deteriorate the precision of the measured point cloud along the time. However, the most important step in data capture is to retain the overlaps between the images more than 80% and have a uniformed picture taking style to ensure the possibility of point cloud generation.
- **Outdoors (GPS available):** GPS data is sufficient to ensure precision and define a measurement frame (M), using DJI the resulting measurement frame is with regards to ECEF

(Earth-centered, Earth-fixed). Including markers in the captured scene would just open the possibility to align the measurement frame automatically. The common recommendations of outdoor data capture are relatively the same as indoor data capture. However, in order to retain the overlaps properly from the DJI, the distance in both directions, sideways and upwards with regarding to the structure scanned, can be computed and used by the DJI in order to capture images according to the computed distances to ensure the proper overlaps.

2.4.2. Cleaning & Cropping the interested areas of point cloud (point cloud)

After the point cloud has been calculated from a photogrammetry software (PIX4D), the result is a raw point cloud. The point cloud will contain mostly the components in the interested areas, where the image acquisition takes place. However, there will be some unwanted point clouds floating around. It could be the components seen in the images far away and not in the interested area. This requires a manual cropping process, which can be done in PIX4D software by defining a process area. Moreover, if the point cloud needs to be cleaned, for example, unwanted floating point clouds in the interested area, a manual deleting process can be done in this step before exporting the measured and cleaned point cloud to the other processes.

2.4.3. Aligning measured data to the BIM-model (photos and point clouds)

2.4.3.1 Photos

Using Exif Metadata (Exchangeable Image File Format) to store and share position and orientation of the point of view.

- Actual workflow:
 - The point cloud and the position and orientation *.txt file generated share a common measurement frame (M).
 - Use Kabsch's algorithm to align the measurement frame (M) to the reference frame (R) from the BIM model based on at least 4 measured points which are visible in the point cloud and the *.ifc model.
 - Store the position and the orientation in the Exif data user comment.

2.4.3.2 Point Clouds

- Actual workflow:
 - Use Kabsch's algorithm to align the measurement frame (M) to the reference frame (R) from the BIM model based on at least 4 measured points which are visible in the point cloud and the *.ifc model.
 - Transform the point cloud to the reference frame (R).

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

- Option 1: Use a simple python script to transform smaller point cloud data sets. TODO: Extend this so it can also handle larger point cloud data sets. Extend this so it can handle big translations.
- Option 2: Use CloudCompare to transform bigger point cloud data sets. TODO: Extend this so it can handle big translations.

2.4.3.3 Point of View of photos on VIAS Site

Figure 14 a) Indoors: Point of View photos used for `t_Stairs.las`, b) Outdoors: Point of View photos used for `t_SideView.las`

2.4.3.4 Results point cloud alignment on VIAS Site

Figure 15 a) Indoors: `t_Stairs.las` vs. `Architecture_zeroed_from_rev_0.ifc`, b) Outdoors: `t_SideView.las` vs. `Architecture_zeroed_from_rev_0.ifc`

2.4.4. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Data capture for detecting safety nets, VIAS-site, Spain	Successful data capture with commercial drones. Development of post processing the position data to BIM-coordinate frame.	For future data capture, defined markers will be used that are known by the BIM and measured precisely on site. These than can be integrated into the alignment

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
		workflow in an automated fashion (the current workflow is prone to errors). Develop software so that the received data (photos and point clouds) are transformed automatically to the reference frame.

2.5. IR - Image data capture

For fire hazards on the construction site, the same applies as everywhere else: the earlier they are detected, the better and the lower the consequential damage. For this reason, drones and robots are to be used to detect potential hazards and sources of fire with the help of IR cameras. Typically, these occur after welding work, or at disposal points with combustible material (packaging material, paper). For this the drone, which usually carries an optical camera, is equipped with an IR camera (FLIR Vue Pro) and the gimbal was adapted accordingly (see image below).

2.5.1. FLIR Vue Pro thermal camera

The chosen Camera has a resolution of 640 x 512px and is mounted to the custom made 2DOF gimbal system. The power supply and the data transfer go via a mini-USB connector to the drone control unit (Raspberry pi 4), whereas the photo capture is triggered by a PWM signal from the flight controller. Currently the IR photos do not directly have an associated position as the outdoor photos have. In principle, this is possible to redirect, but is currently not yet implemented.

Figure 16 The new generation of the 2DOF gimbal equipped with the FLIR Vue IR camera.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

In the present test case, initial tests were carried out in the ZHAW laboratory. Heating radiators and a warm construction site lamp were selected as the "hot material" here.

Figure 17 Thermal and corresponding standard images from the ZHAW lab

Photos above show views with IR- and standard photo cameras. In the IR image, the color scaling is automatically done "from coldest to hottest", therefore the radiators appear in different colours in the two images. In a post-processing, critical objects can be detected automatically if necessary and warnings can be sent. However, this functionality is not implemented yet.

2.5.2. FLIR Ax8 thermal camera (Ground Robot)

The chosen camera, as described in Section 2.1, offers both visible and thermal images that can now be acquired directly as a ROS topic through the ethernet camera driver.

Main features to highlight are:

- AUTOMATIC ANALYSIS AND ALARMS

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

With its streaming video output, the AX8 not only gives you live video of every installation, but it also provides automated alarming when pre-set temperature thresholds are exceeded as well as temperature trend analysis.

- INDUSTRIAL PROTOCOL

Since FLIR AX8 is Ethernet/IP and Modbus TCP compliant analysis and alarm results can easily be shared. Digital inputs/outputs are available for alarms and control of external equipment. An image masking function allows you to select only the relevant part of the image for your analysis.

Figure 18 Optical and IR-image in Robotnik lab

2.5.3. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
IR - Image data capture	IR photos can be taken, the drone can quickly be adapted for that case.	<p>Automated data transfer from camera to backend.</p> <p>Drone: specific path planning for IR photo capture.</p> <p>Automated data processing of IR-images, detecting critical/hot regions.</p>

2.6. Indoor Positioning System

The indoor positioning system device for localisation of workers is based upon Bluetooth devices, according to the setup detailed in deliverable D5.3 Ethics and Data Management Plan. These poses no interference problems to other devices nearby. It offers low installation and maintenance cost. Similarly, there is wide use of Bluetooth integrated technology that are easily accessible and can be used for future research purpose along with the current localisation system. The devices used in BIMprove are the BluEpyc BLE devices for indoor localisation. The BLE devices consist of three main components. Gateway (reader), Echo Beacons and beacons.

Gateway (reader):

The model of the gateway used is BE-BLEG-WE5.1. It is an indoor wall mounted gateway that supports Bluetooth 5.1 and is integrated with 1 antenna. It has functionality of both gateway and reader i.e., it is capable to read data from other BLE devices (beacons and echo beacons) and transmit the collected data to a Host (Connected PC) using TCP/IP protocol. It has read range up to 100 meters with transmission power of +3dbm and has receiving sensitivity of -85 dbm to -91dbm. It requires an external 12 to 24V DC power source.

Echo Beacons:

Echo beacons are BLE devices that scans for the beacons within an area and allows identification and localisation of the beacons. The echo beacons receive data from the beacons and re-transmit the collected beacons data to the Reader. The model of Echo beacons used is BE-EB5.WM.1. It supports Bluetooth 5.1 and has transmission power that can be varied from -20 dBm to +8 dBm. The transmission range is up to 200 meters and has several configuration parameters to filter the beacons based upon RSSI values, advertising masks, whitelists, and blacklists. It requires an external DC power source of 12 to 24 V.

Beacons:

These are BLE mobile devices that' sends advertising data with limited energy consumption. The rate of advertising interval and transmission power can be configured using 'LightBlue', mobile application. The transmission distance is up to 120 meter and has 4 level of transmission power that can be selected (-23dB, -6dB, 0dB and 4dB). It utilizes 3V DC power source and weight about 4.2 g with size of 31mm in diameter a 10 mm thickness.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 19 BLE Indoor Positioning device

The indoor localisation gateway device collects the worker location data and saves it to .txt format on the host computer. In our context the host is a PC to which the gateway was connected through Ethernet. The csv data was then exported to SQL server database using Python script. The python script was used to filter the data and transfer it from .txt file to SQL server database. Once the data were arranged to database table it was than ready to be picked up for visualisation by any of the BIMprove applications.

2.6.1. Dataflow and overview of data processing steps in the PoC setup

Figure 20 Data processing in PoC

In order to visualise the localisation data, it was necessary to separate particular area for each Echo Beacons. So, the model of the test room was modified in Revit and included zone area with diameter of 1.5m allocated for each of the Echo Beacons. To represent Echo Beacons and gateway a custom object from electrical fixture family was created in Revit and zones were represented using object from the Revit floor family. Then 3D view of the model was exported to format that is supported by Navisworks. The figure below shows the layout of Echo Beacons, zones and gateway in the test room model.

Figure 21 Indoor positioning PoC layout

Figure 22 Visualisation of localisation data

2.6.2. Results

Main purpose of the experiment was to test accuracy of the worker positioning device for the developed system, test the reliability of the generated data from the device and estimate overall delay of the system in the given set up. These were defined as follows:

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the device for the system was percentage of measurements within which the devices were able to detect the target. It was calculated using following equation:

$$Accuracy = \frac{Available\ readings}{Total\ number\ of\ readings} \times 100\%$$

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Reliability:

Reliability referred to percentage measurement within which the system effectively detected the target in the locations and visualised them. Following equation was used for its calculation:

$$\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{Available readings} - (\text{False readings} + \text{overlap readings})}{\text{Total number of readings}} \times 100\%$$

It was necessary to find the parameters constituting the equations shown above.

For this, the collected data from observation tables of each target were thoroughly analysed using the recorded video of the experiment and database query. These parameters were defined as follows:

- a) Available reading: These are the number of readings that were visualised by the system in the model. The count of available readings was generated from the database using SQL query.
- b) Number of Blind readings: The readings were counted as Blind readings if the beacons were present in the zone but were not visualised in the model. These readings were counted manually when the plugin displayed the message of 'no recent data in the zone' even if the target was present.
- c) Total number of readings: It is the sum of available readings and blind readings.
- d) Number of False readings: The readings were counted as false readings if the targets were visualised in the zone's despite of their presence. These readings were counted manually when the plugin displayed the tag name of the target and highlighted the zones even if it was not there.
- e) Overlap readings: These are the counts of readings for which a target is visualised in both of the zones at the same time. These readings were counted manually.

2.6.2.1 Single target tests

Both over all Accuracy and Reliability of the system was found to be 87.96 %. The obtained values resulted to be same as no false and overlap readings were seen with single target localisations.

Only blind readings were obtained with one-person localisation. The blind reading could have been resulted when zone sensors were not able to receive the signals from the target. It is to be noted that the zone sensors were configured to receive signals from the target with RSSI value greater than -55db any target with RSSI values less than -55db are filtered out. The phenomena of multi-path fading are often observed in small and confined room where the received signal strengths fluctuates rapidly, and the received signal level could be both constructive or destructive due to the characteristic of multi-path fading signals arriving at the receiver antenna. This could have resulted in lower RSSI value or signal strengths, or the placement of person could have been little farther

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

away from the sensor range in the first set up. The delay or the response time for the system varied from 1 to 5 sec with single target arrangement where 5 secs was rare occurrence.

2.6.2.2 Double target tests

The overall accuracy of the system was found to be 93.11 % and Reliability was 89.89%. Both False and overlap readings were obtained in this set up. The false reading could have been resulted due to higher RSSI values or strong signal strength of the target received by the corresponding zone sensors. Usually, the sensor receives strong signal strength from the target nearest to it and data transfer and filter program filters the data based upon their RSSI values and allocate it to respective zones as shown Figure 21.

However, at some instant if the signal strengths received by another zone sensor is higher than the signal strength of the sensors nearer to the target false readings are obtained. Such phenomena are common where the space are constraints and sensors are placed close to each other. Only 5 overlap readings were noted throughout the test and all with 2 people localisation set up. The possible reasons could be due to equal signal strength received by both the zone sensors resulting in to same RSSI values, Because of this the program could not distinguish between them and overlap readings are seen. The response time of system with double target was found to be varying from 1 to 22 sec, this could be due to congestion of the data in gateway buffer, with more readings. This can be minimised through proper configuration of the device parameters like scan an advertising interval.

2.6.3. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Indoor Positioning System	Satisfactory accuracy and reliability of the system in different cases	Field tests, installation on site.

3. Data Processing and Evaluation

3.1. Detecting Safety Nets

Risk Object Visual Analysis System, ROVAS, bases on the convolutional neural networks, CNN, for its visual object detection task. CNN based AI/ML models are commonly used in modern computer vision systems and object detection.

The images captured from the risk zones can be analysed by the ROVAS for detecting the existence and placement of the required safety structures. The safety structures are expected to mitigate various risks on the construction site locations, e.g. fire or fall risks. The ROVAS can make only positive detections, i.e. confirming the existence of such structures and thus aid inspecting safety structures' readiness state in the locations for safe construction work.

The REST based service interface with JSON formatted response from the ROVAS, is described in the Deliverable D2.5 Safety-critical Situation Detection. The returned JSON result encodes the following detection parameters, if any, as described in the Deliverable 2.4 Detailed Description of the Safety Functionalities and Worker Notifications. These include the following attributes:

- **Class** – object class: barrier=0 | safety_net=1 | garbage=2
- **Confidence** – detection confidence from 0-1.0
- **Name** – human readable name for the detect object class
- **x1** – upper left corner x-coordinate of the bounding box
- **y1** – upper left corner y-coordinate of the bounding box
- **x2** – lower right corner x-coordinate of the bounding box
- **y2** – lower right corner y-coordinate of the bounding box

The coordinates are counted as pixels that of the original image dimensions. Translation to a global or construction site coordinate system requires additional calculations with the direction and location of the camera with the physical characteristics of the optical system. All confidence results over 0.5 can be considered quite reliable detections.

3.1.1. Evaluation Metrics

The maturity of the AI/ML model in ROVAS can be evaluated only by relational development of the achieved accuracy and loss indicators. This is since systems to compare to are mostly non-existent and there are no common publicly shared datasets for rating CNN models in this specific application domain. The results achieved are thus valid only in the BIMprove dataset and global validity cannot be guaranteed without much more extensive testing.

In the evaluation process of the object detection computer vision models several various metrics are used generally. These are common indicators demonstrating the model's learning development trend and suggesting or predicting the final detection accuracy at its best. The following or their combinations have been used here:

- **Intersection-over-union** – IoU or also known as Jaccard index. Is a metric to evaluate similarity of the human labelled ground truth bounding box to the model predicted one. IoU gets value of 1.0 in a perfect match. For more information see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jaccard_index
- **Precision** – P - used and defined here as a fraction of retrieved documents that are relevant to the query. Particularly, in this case it is a fraction of the correctly predicted objects in the image out of all predicted objects. Correctly predicted objects are determined based on the ground truth in the human labelled dataset.
- **Recall** – R – used and defined as the fraction of the relevant documents that are successfully retrieved. Particularly, in this case it is a fraction of the correctly predicted objects in the image out of the objects that were supposed to be predicted in the image. Correctly predicted and predictable objects are determined based on the ground truth in the human labelled dataset.
- **Precision-recall** – PR – is a graph plotting the relationship between achieved precision, P, and recall, R. The area under the PR curve represents the achieved average precision for the individual classes and of which mean is the mean average precision for all classes. See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Precision_and_recall for more information regarding precision, recall and precision-recall.
- **mAP** - Mean Average Precision calculated as the mean of the average precision for all detected classes. Additionally mAP@05 and mAP@05-095 use additional threshold criteria for all detected object classes as IoU of 0.5 or 0.5-0.95, respectively. According to the <https://hasty.ai/content-hub/mp-wiki/metrics/map-mean-average-precision> the state-of-the-art mAP for the object detection task on the COCO dataset's test part is currently equal to 0.631. See same
- **Losses**
Losses in machine learning are model specific variously calculated values representing error or difference between the predicted value and the ground truth in the labelled training data in the case of supervised learning.
- **Overfitting**
As the overall accuracy is the main metric, the validation losses indicate development of the model's generalization ability impacting to the validated accuracy. The converging validation losses usually indicate that the potentially achievable peak accuracy for the model is being reached. This is dependent on the model capacity, used training data, hyperparameters and

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

other training settings. The increasing validation losses usually may indicate overfitting and thus inadequate ability to generalize or really learn from data. Overfitted model achieves very high accuracy on the training set but severely losses it in the practical use.

3.1.2. Evaluation Results

The machine learning based computer vision model used in ROVAS was trained with the dataset and parameters as described in the deliverable D2.5 Safety Critical Situation Detection.

The training process was continuously monitored and evaluated with the performance metrics as explained in the preceding section. The training was continued for 200 epochs, or timesteps during which all the data is consumed once, around which the validation losses started converging or even rising. For comparative reasons, the training was concluded with the image sizes of 960 x 960 and the default 640 x 640. The results are shown in the Fig. 23 and Fig. 24, the development of the mean accuracy, mAP, during training and the final precision-recall, PR, for both image sizes.

Figure 23 Developing Mean Average Precision, $mAP@0.5$ and $mAP@0.95$ with 960x960 and 640x640 image input sizes. The achieved maximum $mAP@0.5$ is around 0.75 and a little less than 0.5 for the 960x960 and 640x640 image sizes, respectively. The $mAP@0.5-0.95$ reaches levels of over 0.5 and 0.25, respectively.

Figure 24 Final precision-recall graphs for detected object classes with a) 960x960 and b) 640x640 image input sizes. The model reaches 0.946 and 0.696 mean average precision, mAP for safety-net detection depending on the image size used. Results are after 200 training epochs using the best model achieved during the training.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Similarly, the validation losses for the 960x960 and 640x640 image sizes are presented in the Fig. 25. The losses for the smaller image size starts to diverge after convergence around 100 epochs. Continuing training for the larger image size may improve resulting accuracy slightly but only after a much longer training period.

Figure 25 Validation losses reached on the validation data subset for the image sizes of 960x960 and 640x640 pixels.

3.1.3. Evaluation Conclusions

It is apparent that the overall precision increases with the increased image size. The large high-definition images with proper lightning makes the detectable details naturally clearer and thus easier to detect. However, even when using transfer learning approach, as described in D2.5 Safety Critical Situation Detection, with moderate number of training epochs, the consumption of the computing resources is high and resulting overall run time is long. The 640x640 transfer learning session of 200 epochs lasted for over 24 hours with moderately high-performance GPU acceleration capability offered by Nvidia Quadro RTX 5000 and 16 GB of dedicated RAM. A similar training session with 960x960 images lasted for over 86 hours. These times applied only after finding a working and reasonable training setting. Several completed training and retraining sessions were required during the project to find parameters used here and especially determine the impact of the updating and increasing data set.

Interpreting the precision and loss curves suggest that the further training may improve the overall accuracy a little bit further. But it may also prove to be unjustified use of computing resources regarding the levels of achievable improvements. So far, the best available model was the large YOLO model type consuming images of 960x960. It was able to reach reasonable accuracy levels without regressing to overfitting. Anyhow, the completed training cycles and trialled options show that the best improvements in accuracy would be the utilization of larger image resolutions.

Larger images sizes could be used to fully exploit the HD or 4K resolutions for even higher accuracy. But that would come at the cost of the severely extended training time at least with the available computing resources. So far, the available dataset may prove to be large enough to train a YOLO based model from scratch for the best possible accuracy. That is of course on provision that some

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

serious amounts of computing power and time would be available. This would include also evolving specifically suitable and more optimal hyperparameters for this case. Yet another option providing room for the accuracy improvement is using some other type than the YOLO type of the CNN models. The benefit of the YOLO based models is its throughput capacity suitable even for the real-time video processing. This of course comes with the cost of some accuracy penalty.

Still, the results may vary significantly in practise as most of the available training data was quite homogeneous in image quality, lightning conditions, certain detectable objects' symmetry in shape and scenery composition. The training dataset's homogeneity has negative impact on the model's general accuracy in the real-world usage with more varying image qualities and contents.

3.1.4. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Detecting Safety Nets	Satisfactory reliability of the system for safety fences and nets.	Training with additional data

3.2. Scan versus plan

A key point in BIMprove is to use reality capture on the construction site to gather data. This includes laser scanning with robots and photo geometry with flying drones. The resulting point clouds are in known positions in space in separate coordinate systems to start with, and we then convert them to the same coordinate system as the BIM-models. To check for progress for a building element that should be complete, we start by getting the oriented bounding box from the BIM, and then (with a little tolerance in all directions) collect the points that are within this box. Based on testing with a structural model, this simple approach work well for many elements, but does of course conceptually have potentially a "loose fit" with non-convex shapes. This is not a problem though, since the visualisation of these point cloud vs the BIM-object in a viewer can work well for a human. In addition, we are working on taking this further by investigating the distances between observed points and the expected surfaces. For several reasons, there could be a large share of a building objects that is not close to scan points. This could be that the scanning has only been done from one side (typically for walls where often one side is exposed, at least for the robot that has to stay on the built floor), or it could be because of shadows (something is in the way between a scan point and the object). Or, it could be that the object is not finished or it does not have correct position or shape.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 26 Matching points (shown here in total) after BIM-based oriented bounding box mapping

Figure 27 Residual points after BIM-based oriented bounding box mapping. Viewed from a different angle than Fig. 26

We are working on creating indicators of how well the scan indicates correctness, but a scan-vs-plan object will also be presented to a human (see "daily decisions" below) for visual inspection and decision.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 28 Comparing scan vs plan manually in the model server GUI. The column "inside" the point cloud is selected with its green highlight colour showing through.

Figure 29 Same as in panel a, but with the point cloud points being semi-transparent.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Fig. 28 and 29 above shows a visual comparison. According to this visual comparison, the shape and position seems correct, and the column seems to have been completed in time (but the outer shaping/protecting layer is still present)

3.2.1. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Scan versus plan	Core approach for sectioning point cloud into BIM-object based parts works well	Further improve algorithms. Add better visualization and decision support for comparison regarding progress and correctness. Integrate with other parts of the system

3.3. BIMprove and the web application

The BIMprove system uses Bimsync as its model server, BCF-server and point cloud server. But backend itself adds support for the other parts of the BIMprove system, and also provides a web-based user interface to the system. The most parts of BIMprove are in the satellites described above, and in systems running inside the backend to do processing - and how it all works together as a whole.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Figure 30 The start page of the BIMprove web application

The start page of the BIMprove web application presents the construction projects inside the system (most of them currently test projects). From here the user can select a project, and it is at project level most of the interesting parts of BIMprove will be available. Projects in BIMprove maps id-wise 1:1 with projects in the model server (Bimsync) - same project id (a GUID).

3.3.1. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
BIMprove and the web application	Web application is being implemented, start page and scheduling page are present in initial versions. Project list is synced with the model server, support for importing schedules to the server	Add the other needed pages and complete the current ones. Make available info from other parts of BIMprove.

3.4.1. Summary

PoC description		Main Result	Open Points
Scheduling	linked with BIM	Be able to view the schedule and BIM-models together, and link tasks with objects in the BIM.	Make the GUI richer, and integrate it the endpoints to the tasks+bim-links database. Move from top level to project level in the GUI. Also further development in general to make it work better. Possibly add support for 4D-IFC.

3.5. Daily Decisions

Figure 32 User interface in the BCF server (Bimsync) of the issues created in one of the BIMprove test projects

The figure above shows an issueboard ("project" in BCF terminology) in the Bimsync Arena GUI. This can be used as a GUI until a simple GUI has been created in the BIMprove web application.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

The flow related to the "daily decisions" is that every day where BIMprove has scanned the activities on the site based on what is completed according to the schedule (including pure safety tasks). The resulting information is sent to the backend (sometimes via other parts of the system). This includes scans from the robots and the drones, labelled photos from the AI and thermographic photos.

The idea is that after construction has ended for the day (1700 hours for instance), the scanning activities is carried out with the drone and the robot resulting in BIM-aligned point clouds, photos and thermo-photos. This is sent to the backend, where processing is done including comparing as-built (point cloud) with as planned (BIM). The result of this processing is a set of BCF issues with links to the underlying information and where possible also using the viewpoint-feature in BCF.

The next morning the decision maker can open his BIMprove issue board and go through the issues that have been created as a result of processing during the night. For the scan vs plan issues, each BCF task will be added and linked to existing information from the considered processing phase. Typical evaluations are: "Was the internal wall completed according to the schedule?" or "Has it got the correct position and shape?"

Figure 33 Screenshot of a task for the decision maker to consider (currently in the model server GUI)

The issue in the figure above shows an issue the decision maker has to consider in the morning.

This person (this role, can be several that take the task) is asked to consider the following for each plan vs scan issue (Work In Progress):

Table 1 The decision makers has to make a choice on how to proceed

Please check if following is as it should be
--

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

- The schedule indicated what work on this was completed yesterday. Is it?
- Is the position correct?
- Is the shape correct?
- Are there any other problems you detect?

The conclusion of your consideration is to decide a status and assign the task to someone if you cannot close it as "Correct according to BIM and schedule"

Possible follow ups can include

- asking for a new scan
- asking a human to go there and check manually, and add one or more photos to document
- it is not complete, so it might be necessary to change the (micro) schedule?
- The shape or position is significantly wrong, so request re-work
- The shape or position is significantly wrong, so change the as-built BIM model
- The shape or position is not perfectly correct, but we accept it, document it, and move on as complete.

Notice that BCF supports user defined (project defined) status-lists and type-lists. This together with assigning task, linking BIM and documents etc. supports a semi-structured workflow that can be supported by the system, but is also human friendly.

3.5.1. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Daily decisions	The "decision maker" gets input from scan vs plan and other sources, and makes his/her decision based on what is observed.	Many required components do exist, most need further work but integration has started. Currently the BCF GUI is using the one from Bimsync Arena, but the plan is to create a built in one in the BIMprove web application (but all data are in sync since Bimsync is also the BCF server).

3.6. Virtual Reality

The BIMprove VR-Viewer (or XR-Viewer, respectively) was introduced in previous deliverables, most notably maybe with the demonstration video as part of the first version D3.1 Technology Demonstrations (). It enables users to view BIM-models and point clouds in VR (or on a PC in the style of a 3D computer game) in single- or multi-user-sessions. So, for many of the PoC use cases described above, the VR-Viewer provides the means for an additional eye-test in a 1:1-scale environment, where decision makers can discuss aligned models and point clouds.

3.6.1. Testing methods and results

Developing and testing a multi-user and multi-device real-time visualisation system that is to be used multi-locally is quite a complex task. In addition to the "normal" problems that can occur and need to be tested for, like possible errors on the level of scripts (code) or usability issues with the graphical user interface, there can be problems with real time visualisation, between-user-synchronisation, and between-device-synchronisation.

To tackle this, the testing of the system has been divided into three types of testing, carried out by three different roles:

1. Testing on the level of code (Debugging), done by the developers themselves.
2. Usability testing, done through expert tests and user tests (see below);
3. Performance tests for real-time visualisation capability (see below).

3.6.2. Usability expert tests

These tests are executed in tight iterations with development. Both summative tests of general user workflows and formative tests on newly developed functionality are performed bi-weekly and the results are fed back directly to the developers and also to the person responsible for the pre-processing of the models.

Examples for results of these are: Lack of self-descriptiveness of interaction techniques (usability), reproduceable synchronisation problems, e.g. can multiple users edit the same data at the same time? cybersickness-inducing lack of real-time performance of certain models etc.

3.6.3. User tests

A first set of usability tests with test users (who were not part of the project) has been carried out in M10 of the project and reported on in earlier deliverables.

Extensive usability tests were planned for M17 (January 2022), but had to be postponed to late February, due to the pandemic. Please see the plan for these tests on the Table 2. The tests are

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

planned to be held in the construction site offices of the VIAS PUC-site in Madrid with six test users of different professions/roles.

Table 2 Planned test for PoC

Phase	Description	Goal/Research Question	Method
Day 1	Single User	Teach and test interaction techniques	
VR-Intro		Get Test person (TP) familiar with VR devices	verbal instructions
1st try & reactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • navigate • explore • model menu handling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • open/close menu • select/deselect models • issue manipulation menu <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • create issues • edit issues • teleport • laser pointer function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get TP to know the functions • Test usability of interaction techniques (How do people get on? Do they remember the techniques intuitively?) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • verbal instructions • Think Aloud (TA), (qualitative)
Questionnaires	Motion sickness	Is motion sickness a problem?	Summarized Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (1 item)
	Sense of presence	Does the system induce a sense of presence?	Summarized Presence Questionnaire (2 items)
Interview		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get general feedback • Would the system help the TP with their work? 	Guided interview

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

Phase	Description	Goal/Research Question	Method
Day 2	Two Users	Test multi-user communication	
VR-Intro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Arrive" in VR Remember interaction techniques 		verbal instructions
Test tasks	Tasks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> find each other explanation and use of laser pointer model menu handling during and as a means of communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> open/close menu select/deselect models issue manipulation menu as a means of communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> create issues edit issues teleport (each other) laser pointer function as a means of communication 		
Questionnaires	Motion sickness	Is motion sickness a problem?	Summarized Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (1 item)
	Sense of group presence	Does the system induce a sense of presence and togetherness?	Summarized Game Experience Questionnaire (2 items)
	SUS	Usability testing	System Usability Scale

Phase	Description	Goal/Research Question	Method
Interview		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Get general feedback• Would the system help the TP with their work?	Guided interview

3.6.4. Performance tests and -optimisation

In software for real-time visualisation of 3D models, there is always a trade-off between geometrical detail, quality, and usability (in the sense of what the user can actually do with the data) of the models on the one hand, and real-time performance and capability on the other hand.

The 3D models (both IFC BIM models and PLY point clouds) are pre-processed to Unity Asset Bundles to work in the BIMprove VR Viewer. (These workflows are currently being documented in the updated (M18) version of Deliverable D2.8.) During this pre-processing, optimisation of the models for real-time rendering can take place. Documented below are some of the different approaches and results that have been tested. This also involves the testing of different available software approaches (e.g. shaders).

3.6.5. BIM models: Optimisation strategies depending on the use case

The performance bottleneck concerning the visualisation of large BIM models is the amount of single graphical objects and not polygon meshes. Hence the amount of polygons is not critical.

In some use cases you may want to have an overview and want to visualize the whole building. For example the transparent architecture superimposed by HVAC / point clouds. Here a pre-processing to combine the meshes with the same material is a good approach. Some models used in BIMprove could be visualized with increased framerates by the factor of 100(!).

In some BIM-related use cases it is necessary to retain the hierarchy of the geometric representation of all building parts to get the link to the related BIM-metadata. In these scenarios the best approach is to filter the building parts, and separate them into smaller "chunks" of geometry, e.g. visualize single storeys only instead of rendering the whole building.

3.6.6. Point Clouds

With point clouds there are two main questions for real-time visualisation: 1) How (much) to reduce them -- to decrease the number of points rendered and therefore the density of the cloud, and thereby

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

increase performance. 2) How to visualise them -- if only points (pixels) are rendered, they are not very well visible, so different shaders can be used, rendering a square or circle per point. This last option, of course, hurts performance.

The following test-example shows this dilemma: The test object in the example below is a point cloud scanned by the Robotnik-robot at the VIAS pilot site. Compared on the table are rendering the point cloud as points or with a circle shader. (Test System: Tested in Unity-Editor 2019.4.28f, DX11; CPU: Intel Core-i7-8700K | GPU: NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080TI | RAM: 64GB).

Table 3 Point cloud dilemma

File	Resolution [mm]	Nr of points [Mio.]	File size PLY [MB]	File size Unity Asset [MB]	Framerate [FPS]
pc_Robotnik_5mm_21_Mio_Circles	5	21	394	174	40
pc_Robotnik_5mm_21_Mio_Points	5	21	394	174	270
pc_Robotnik_10mm_9,7_Mio_Circles	10	9,69	180	84	90
pc_Robotnik_10mm_9,7_Mio_Points	10	9,69	180	84	580
pc_Robotnik_15mm_4,9_Mio_Circles	15	4,9	91	44	190
pc_Robotnik_15mm_4,9_Mio_Points	15	4,9	91	44	1500
pc_Robotnik_20mm_3,7_Mio_Circles	20	3,67	68	34	250
pc_Robotnik_20mm_3,7_mio_Points	20	3,67	68	34	2000

3.6.7. Open points and next steps

The following additional features are under development for the VR Viewer:

- Way-point-system: This will enable the user to define routes or trajectories in VR by simply defining way-points. This functionality could be useful in different PoC use cases, e.g. defining evacuation routes or trajectories in the context of mission planning for UxVs.

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

- Definition of safety features: The VR Viewer already has an "Issue Manipulation Mode" which can be used to mark a specific point in the 3D environment and give it a title and a description text. This functionality will be extended by marking (missing) safety features, like nets, barriers, etc. The user simply defines a plane in 3D space and marks it as "net" or "fence", for example. These objects could then be added to the IFC safety model.
- Integrating BCF: The above mentioned Issue Manipulation Mode will be enhanced so it connects to a BIMprove- (bimsync-) Issue Board and supports the BCF standard. This will support using VR for the Daily Decisions PoC use case.
- Loading from the model- and point-cloud-server through the backend: Since the VR Viewer is developed using the Unity game engine, the Unity-Editor is used to convert IFC and PLY into binary Unity-asset-bundles. The integration of Unity-Editor and the BIMprove backend will be achieved using a REST-based approach. The backend will send commands to the Unity-Editor to start the processes for importing and converting IFC to Unity-Asset-Bundles. These files will be uploaded into the backend. The Unity-Editor will act as a conversion-server.
- Later on, the VR-Viewer (and potentially other Unity-based visualisation software in the project) will download the respecting Asset-Bundles directly from the backend. This would achieve one more important step towards an integrated BIMprove system.

3.6.8. Summary

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
Virtual Reality	Detailed planning of tests are performed and ready.	Tests will occur at the end Feb., begin of March 2022. See additional points in Section 3.6.7.

4. Summary and evaluation of the proof of concept

The test cases described above show that the basic functionality of the BIMprove system is given. The individual subareas are shown again in the following table.

Table 4 Summary of PoC results

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
1. Spatial Data Capture with Ground Robots	5 waypoints missions and point cloud bundle retrieved. Position data linked to images.	Alignment of coordinate frames. Scan data optionally fetched automatically was not always working. API to be checked. Missions imported through backend.
2. Evacuation Route Check	Alarms and pictures taken successfully. Optimal paths calculated and followed in simulation.	Routes to be shared in visualization tool (VR). Alternate exits included in the optimal paths.
3. Spatial Data Capture with Drones	Semi-autonomous drone flight, path planning from application.	Coordinate frames alignment, quality of p.c. (density and precision). When the captured data and the BIM are properly aligned, the results are satisfactory. A yet unsolved problem is the quality of point clouds, if lighting conditions are bad or there are mainly homogeneous surfaces (which will be the case on construction sites).
4. Data capture for detecting safety nets, VIAS-site, Spain	Successful data capture with commercial drones. Development of post processing the position data to BIM-coordinate frame.	For future data capture, defined markers will be used that are known by the BIM and measured precisely on site. These than can be integrated into the alignment workflow in an automated fashion (the current workflow is prone to errors). Develop software so that the received data (photos and point clouds) are transformed automatically to the reference frame.
5. IR - Image data capture	IR photos can be taken, the drone quickly be adapted for that case.	Automated data transfer from camera to backend Drone: specific path planning for IR photo capture

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
		automated data processing of IR-images, detecting critical/hot regions
6. Indoor Positioning System	Satisfactory accuracy and reliability of the system in different cases	Field tests, installation on site.
7. Detecting Safety Nets	Satisfactory reliability of the system for safety fences and nets.	Training with additional data.
8. Scan versus plan	Core approach for sectioning point cloud into BIM-object based parts works well.	Further improve algorithms. Add better visualization and decision support for comparison regarding progress and correctness. Integrate with other parts of the system.
9. BIMprove and the web application	Web application is being implemented, start page and scheduling page are present in initial versions. Project list is synced with the model server, support for importing schedules to the server.	Add the other needed pages and complete the current ones. Make available info from other parts of BIMprove.
10. Scheduling linked with BIM	Be able to view the schedule and BIM-models together, and link tasks with objects in the BIM.	Make the GUI richer, and integrate the endpoints to the tasks+bim-links database. Move from top level to project level in the GUI. Also further development in general to make it work better. Possibly add support for 4D-IFC.
11. Daily Decisions	The "decision maker" gets input from scan vs plan and other sources, and makes his/her decision based on what is observed.	Many required components do exist, most need further work but integration has started. Currently the BCF GUI is using the one from Bimsync Arena, but the plan is to create a built in one in the

D3.3 Proof of concept system description and test results

PoC description	Main Result	Open Points
		BIMprove web application (but all data are in sync since Bimsync is also the BCF server).
12. Virtual Reality	Detailed planning of tests are performed and ready.	Tests will occur at the end Feb., begin of March 2022. See additional points in Section 3.6.7.

